

Analysis ' Melting ' Power: Literature, Subjectivity Liquid , and Resistance against the Cultural and State Powers in the Perspective Postcolonial by Ikwon Setiawan

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Abstract

This article , with theoretical-conceptual and methodological orientation , will discuss fluidity of cultural and state power . By using postcolonial approach , literary narrative can be positioned as a representation product that presents a fluid subjectivity as narrative character and particular discourse , related to socio-cultural problems, especially cultural hybridity . The presence of modernity and the maintaining of traditional cultures in postcolonial society cause such a problem. This study shows that the fluid subjectivity , in one side , emerges emancipation discourse for empowering local society and , in other side , can emerge resistance against such cultural-based-power . The binary opposition between the West and the East is becoming fluid , because postcolonial subject can use modern thoughts-although not completely-to deconstructing the wholeness of both modernity and traditional cultures . However , when the state applies neo-liberalism , the concept of fluid subjectivity and cultural hybridity need to be re-interpreted . The power of culture and state will get new meaning and resistance because individual freedom principle in market law demands the minimum presence of the two entities . Such condition emerge a chance to criticize and modify postcolonial studies .

Keywords: *narrative structure , fluid subjectivity , resistance , postcolonial studies , neo - liberalism .*

INTRODUCTION

In a conversation with Jean Comaroff about "decentralization subject" in public postcolonial, Hommi K Bhabha, one of the thinker postcolonial from India, says as following. As subject ever experience colonization, society postcolonial always experience betweenness, ambivalence, and duplicity cultural because imitation to modern culture and wishes for permanent operate part culture traditional, so produce hybridity cultural. Meanwhile, thoughts postcolonialism position defocused subjectivity as tactics subversive to power dominant colonizers /Western, in this writing I argue that in literary narrative a can also be used for read how subject narrative and practice discursive in literary work "thaw" budava traditional and country.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

A. Literary Narratives of Space-Between and Postcolonial Studies

Postcolonial studies with draft theoretical betweenness, duplicity, ambivalence, mimicry, mockery, and hybridity can presenting rich and critical literary analysis. In condition non-subjectivity centered, culture public colonial and postcolonial Becomes hybrid. Practice discriminatory colonial positioning subject colonized as different from subjectivity invaders because ongoing binary difference got disturbance from practice imitation that produces hybridity. In In such a perspective, literary works are product representation that presents problems social, cultural, economic, political, religious and gender, in public postcolonial, especially related how subjects figure narrative position selfhood they are in the middle meeting Among modern and traditional values, between the individual and the communal / nation, as well as between the local and the global/metropolitan within variety formation discursive. Trend the many represented in literary works written by writers from a country- mostly from Asia, Africa, and Latin America--who migrated and lived in the metropolitan areas of developed countries, in particular Western Europe, United States, Canada, and Australia-- or usual called diaspora'. As migrant from Pakistan living in England, Rusdhie, as represented by the characters fictitious, of course understand its geo-cultural position in the so-called metropolitan range with corner look middleman because he find many individual from the former country invaders and individuals from former countries colony English with variety variant the culture. Mixtures between culture parent and culture origin that 's what will give birth to "newness" for the melting world Binary boundaries of West and East, though permanent colored voltages non-existent articulation stop. More from simply reading to representation complexity identity and subjectivity culture, perspective Colonialism also opened itself up to the emergence of "gaps" theoretical" when linked with complexity that.

B. 'Melting' Culture in Will Be Modern

of two above framework, culture traditional no only interpreted as values, practices, and growing confidence in society, but also expand in aspects others, gender for example. Saying women is discourse about spirit resistance a child woman to binary opposition between subject boy and subject girl-as crutch main continuity power

patriarchal-through two way . Displacement to in different " space " and " place " - college high in Koa Yogyakarta-- from cottage boarding school salafi , after the divorce with Samsudin , have deliver a modern world full of offer enlightenment to in her mind as a female . A world, a thoughts , and a feeling middle changed along with entry subject women to in the space and time filled modern spirit . Lectures , activities organizations , and activities write is a process of " being " with mind " which makes women as " girl new "; a woman who should go out from power tradition and can develop all intelligence and ability based on power reason . Subjectivity women changed become very fluid , no want to restrained by codes traditional only _ oppress girl , but no means a no want bound with institution traditional , like family heterosexual . Will being modern also implies existence power reason for release subject man from restraint religious power . Religious arguments , such as hadith , share women not knowledge that must positioned as truth should reinterpreted with " common sense wal afiat " in the middle spirit changing times. How to read from the liminal range in study postcolonial , with so , apart from can presenting wealth and ' preoccupation ' analysis in see middlemanship and hybridity cultural , too, once again , can bring up gap theoretical . In people who still put forward tradition patriarchy , like in the case experienced Annisa , choice for Act in framework modernity made by the characters narrative-against nor transform the traditional - is shape struggle for give strengthening to group social experience _ oppression . No can denied connectedness author with discourses _ _ emancipatory , like feminism , will influence presence lawsuit to establishment tradition that has considered as regime truth .

C. ' The Melting ' of the State in Neoliberal Desire

System applied political economy in post- colonial countries must also be careful _ when talk about position subject narrative in literary work because he will Becomes condition socio-historical background of the creative process a author . Moment this , neoliberalism or economy political based on the law of the market is systems applied in developed countries . of the four the neoliberal principle , individualism as philosophy believes _ _ Enlightenment and movement modernism as the basis of birth liberalism - modified thinking _ in neoliberalism - is knowledge key in formation spreading discursive _ to in practice economics , politics , and socio-cultural . As for the modifications made is more individualism _ attached to market mechanism as regime truth and accommodation to culture local for expansion capitalism . In framework think Thus , structure literary narrative will bring up two possibility practice discursive in positioning traditional and state power in the middle _ market capitalism . First , some values and practice traditional will permanent raised for build logic narrative reasonable maybe in the middle struggle individual for forge dir so you can realize his ideals . Novel Garuda in My Chest can Becomes example how read third practice discursive above . _ Bayu , a teenager from a sub-urban village in Jakarta, aspires to for to be member national team junior football . However , the aspiration got hindrance from Hated Grandpa _ profession footballer because _ considered no can presenting prosperity for himself in the future . What's interesting from this novel is meet him individual desire-- to be member junior national team- with ambition

nationality , bring fragrant Indonesian name in competition international football . _ Country, then , enough presented as " red white " or " garuda " which will always flown , accompanying struggle Bayu and his friends in the national team when compete oppose team from another country.

CONCLUSION

When neoliberalism with all formation discursive in practice government - than and life daily community , study postcolonial need give suppressor - an more critical to structure literary narrative . Discourses the middle shape subjects discursive , including author and character narrative his design , which is connected by reasonable with idealization - neoliberal idealization in looking at culture and country. As study explorative oriented conceptual-theoretical with a little example implication methodologically , this article is still need deepening and elaboration related betweenness , ambivalence , and hybridity cultural in structure literary narratives , in particular related background condition socio - historical application neoliberalism . Very again , neoliberalism as ideology political economy and formation very fluid discursive in accommodate culture local , state, and individual desire is a stretches and challenges new must _ Keep going criticized , even from vantage point very personal life of figure narrative.

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